

**PERSPECTIVES OF BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP
DEVELOPMENT: DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION
FOR BUSINESS MODEL INNOVATION**

Economic, Management, Finance and System Engineering
from the Academic and Practitioners Views

**COLLECTED ABSTRACTS AND PROGRAMME
OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE**

18TH INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

**PERSPECTIVES OF BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP
DEVELOPMENT: DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION FOR BUSINESS
MODEL INNOVATION:**

**ECONOMIC, MANAGEMENT, FINANCE AND SYSTEM ENGINEERING
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SEPTEMBER 16-17, 2021

BRNO, CZECH REPUBLIC

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CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

Thursday, 16 September		Academic part(in English)
Plenary session		Moderator: Marek Zinecker
<i>11:00 - 11:15</i>	Welcome speech	<i>dean Vojtech Bartos vice-dean Stanislav Skapa</i>
<i>11:15 - 12:30</i>	Panel discussion	<i>Vit Chlebovsky, Robert Zich</i>
<i>12:30 - 13:00</i>	Break with culture programme by students of the Faculty of Business and Management	
Parallel sessions		Moderators
<i>13:00 – 14:30</i>		
	Economic in Digital Transformation	<i>Jana Hornungova (FBM BUT, CZE) Natalja Lace (RTU, LV)</i>
	Finance in Digital Transformation	<i>Ondrej Zizlavsky (FBM BUT, CZE) Zuzana Krizova (FBM BUT, CZE)</i>
	Management in Digital Transformation	<i>Lucie Kanovska (FBM BUT, CZE) David Schuller (FBM BUT, CZE) Jarmila Strakova (ITB, CZE)</i>
	Systems in Digital Transformation	<i>Karel Doubravsky (FBM BUT, CZE) Zuzana Jankova (FBM BUT, CZE) Irada A. Dzhalladova (KNEU, UKR)</i>
	Universities in Digital Transformation	<i>Zdenka Konecna (FBM BUT, CZE) Feybi Ariani Goni (FBM BUT, CZE)</i>
	Master's Degree Students' section	<i>Veronika Bumberova (FBM BUT, CZE) Frantisek Milichovsky (FBM BUT, CZE)</i>
<i>14:30 – 14:45</i>	Break	
Conclusion of conference		Moderator: Marek Zinecker
<i>14:45 – 15:15</i>	Summary of the Day, Sessions Moderators	

Friday, 17 September

Company part (in Czech)

Digital Transformation for Business Model Innovation

What can you expect?

Guidance on how to effectively and purposefully digitise your company in relation to your business model. Sharing of experiences of specific companies, presentation of a tool to verify the digital maturity of the company, design of digital transformation scenarios, and joint discussion on the experience of implementing digitisation.

Plenary session

Moderator: David Schuller

10:00 – 10:20 **Opening and Introductory Remarks on Digital Transformation in the Czech Republic**

Support for digitisation and innovation by the Government of the Czech Republic

Karel Havlicek, Minister of Industry and Trade

Everybody has to go digital. Big and small.

Michal Stefl, Vice President of the Czech Chamber of Commerce

Pavla Breckova, Vice-Chairwoman of the Association of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises and Crafts of the Czech Republic

Digital transformation and Industry 4.0

Josef Bures, Member of the Board of Directors of NC LINE, a.s.

Digital Transformation: “Good Practices”

10:20 - 11:30 Interesting cases of digital transformation solutions for SMEs (from different areas of operation and different company sizes)

Case Study of Digitisation in ASTRA MOTOR

Jan Keprda, Executive Director, ASTRA MOTOR spol. s r.o.

Using the digital twin principle for small series production, the so-called Digital Cockpit 4.0. The new system helps to optimise individual areas of the production process, from planning through technical preparation and machine utilisation monitoring to reporting and providing data for further use or analysis. The entire process is integrated with Astra Motor’s other existing systems.

Case Study of Digitisation in METALKOV

Evzen Reitschlager, Business Director and Executive Director, METALKOV

Break

Experiences from the Implementation of Digitisation of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in the Czech Republic

Frantisek Podzimek, Head of Digital Enterprise, Siemens

Digitisation and automation serve as the key to further growth of companies and enterprises. Together we will present several successful examples from the Czech market.

How can you Save Time and Money when Innovating?

*Martin Frelich, Director of the Research Institute for
Entrepreneurship and Innovation at the Czech Chamber of Commerce*

Accelerate and automate your business. How to do it? Digitise and innovate with powerful tools! Discover the way to digitise efficiently, how to reduce your costs, and how to supplement or save your human workforce.

11:25 - 11:30 Break

11:30 - 12:30 **SME Digital Maturity Measurement Tool and Digital Transformation Scenarios**

Robert Zich, Iveta Simberova, Vit Chlebovsky, Faculty of Business and Management, BUT Brno, Czech Republic

- Introduction of a tool for measuring the digital maturity of SMEs
- Selected digital transformation scenarios

12:30 - 13:00 Break with culture programme by students of the Faculty of Business and Management

Panel Discussion – a Platform for Discussion between Academics and Practitioners on the topic: Experience with the Implementation of Digitisation

13:00 - 14:15 **Chairs:** *Vit Chlebovsky and Robert Zich, FBM, BUT Brno + online inputs from the South Bohemia Region: Jan Vachal, ITB, Ceske Budejovice*

Conclusion

Moderator: *David Schuller*

14:15 Conclusion

Bulgaria in the OECD corporate tax reform: Assessing the opportunity for a 3.0 tax reform

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Abstract

Purpose of the article The OECD has recently launched an epochal reform of the international tax law framework originally established in the early days of the twentieth century. Through its two pillars, the change aims at smoothing the remaining anachronistic assumptions which have made this corpus's approach ineffective. Namely, it addresses the issue of companies' trans-national reach to reduce the room that big corporations have to engage in base erosion and profit shifting (BEPS) to reduce their overall tax burden and gain an undue competitive advantage on less tentacular organisations. Against such a complex background, this paper deals with the need for Bulgaria, one the 130 countries and jurisdictions that accepted the OECD's proposal, to rethink its domestic tax laws. Styling itself as a policy paper, the text analyses two possible policy alternatives: (i) simply propping up the flat corporate-tax rate from 10% to 15% and (ii) restructuring the corporate-tax regime on the American Tax Code's model through higher rates, a deduction for asset depreciation, and other tweaks. The effect of these reforms is evaluated through an appositely ideated model with a neo-classical backbone and a Keynesian Tax-Feedback component. Purpose of the article the article aims at investigating the impact of the recent OECD proposal to reform corporate tax rates on Bulgaria with specific focus on how fiscal policy can both adjust to these changes.

Methodology/methods Through a literature review, the paper will identify some of the key determinants of a schematic neoclassical economic model describing a small, open economy such as Bulgaria's. Then, it will apply construct an original model to assess the effects of the two proposed reforms on wages' and corporate incomes' growth in Bulgaria.

Scientific aim The paper contributes to the extant literature in two ways. First, it summarises the extant literature on neoclassical modelling, focusing on how to integrate discretionary fiscal policy in such a framework. Second, by analysing two simple policy recommendations, it provides a clear guide to Bulgarian policymakers as to how to prepare for the upcoming changes in the international corporate-tax framework — something which, to date, is missing.

Findings Scholars have underutilised neoclassical models in the analyses of small, open economies such as Bulgaria's. Yet, their relative flexibility and the possibility to tweak and further deepen their assumption and functioning makes these model best suited to account for the entanglement of digitalisation, globalisation (both generally and, more specifically, in the guise of EU membership) and post-socialist transformation. On the policies suggested, the restructuring of Bulgaria's corporate tax appears superior (in a Paretian sense) to a mere rate hike. However, political feasibility and international tax competition – including within the EU – make it a rather unlikely realisation in the upcoming months.

Conclusions Due to the relevance of political and societal factors, this paper concludes that small, open economies such as Bulgaria cannot afford to reform their (corporate) tax regime on their own. Rather, they need larger partners (e.g., Germany, France, Italy) and blocks (i.e., the OECD and the EU) to press these changes and guarantee that no unfair competitive advantages will emerge between tightly integrated economies such as those of the EU. The main limitation of this study is potentially also its greatest strength. By focusing on the peculiar case of a small, open economy such as Bulgaria's, it reduces the scope of applicability of its policy recommendations. However, this very narrowness allows the paper to test assumedly consensual theoretical assumptions around model's workability and to provide more 'realistic' policy advice.

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JEL Classification: M15, M21

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